

Brief Research Report

Assessment of Event Decoration Enterprise in Makurdi Metropolis, Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This research examined the assessment of event decoration enterprise in Makurdi metropolis. Specifically, the study seek to find out the types of even decoration arrangement in Makurdi metropolis; determine the type of challenges encountered by event decorators; and suggest possible ways through which these challenges can be minimized to improve event decoration in Makurdi metropolis. The choice of the study came as a result of unemployment in government ministries, thereby necessitating many graduates to venture into event decoration enterprise. The population for the study comprises of event decorators from the registered 115 event decoration ventures in Makurdi. The sample size of 67 was obtained using cluster and purposive sampling. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts in the university. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyze the data. The findings of this study showed that, the types of event decoration enterprise comprise of fabric, flower and balloon among others. The results shows that fabric decoration was rated high with mean score of 3.74. This is because fabrics can be re-used several times for decoration purposes. Possible ways through which decoration enterprise challenges can be minimized include the careful planning of budget which had the highest mean score of 3.67. It was therefore recommended that proper budgeting should be made by providing extra allowance in the budget in case of changes in the price of items in the market.

Keywords: Decoration Enterprise, Event Decoration, Fabrics, Revenue

1. Introduction

Decoration means to make something more attractive on a special occasion; this could mean to transform the venue of an event to look captivating, beautiful and attractive. The special events in which more emphasis is needed include, wedding receptions, conferences, parties or even funeral ceremonies (Walton & Walton, 2005). Event refers to an occasion where people come together to celebrate, worship, honor, remember, and to socialize (Douglas & Derrett, 2001). In other opinion, events are referred to as specific rituals and celebrations that are consciously planned and created to mark special occasions (De Kok, Uhlaner & Thurik, 2003). The important factors to consider in event decoration depend on size and type of events. Major events attract significant number of visitors and the use of media coverage (Lee et al., 2002). Such events include tourism, international sporting events, and political rallies among others. Minor events include weddings, fund raising, charity events, parties and community social events (Landry & Jordre, 1968). Other factors to consider in event decoration are the provision of tents, chairs, furniture, items of decorations, event premises and adequate refreshments (Cakar, Bititci & MacBryde, 2003).

Event decoration has to do with how the interior and the exterior of an event venue are decorated (Nkeonye, 1997). Interior decoration and design is the act of decorating a room, a venue or a place so that it is attractive, easy, to use and functions well with the existing architecture (Ukil, 2016). The role of interior decorator probably came into existence in the 1720s in Western Europe, mostly being performed by men of diverse backgrounds. William Kent, was trained as the first person to take charge of an entire interior, including internal architecture, furniture selection, and the handling of paintings in his own time (Douglas & Derrett, 2001). Designers always pay attention to colour, materials, formation, illumination, and so on, however other senses, such as odor, hearing, haptic, are barely considered (Canavan, 2015). Without non-visual sensory design, interior space would be uncomfortable. Although sight is the most important sense in perceiving the world, other sense systems are also significant. Non-visual sensation can strengthen visual perception, and deliver a distinct identity to an interior space (Berdie & Berdie, 2011). Most importantly, the role of styles, colours and design on the exteriors of a building can never be overemphasized. Through the use of various materials for maintenance and yet glossy look, dampness and rifts in the wall, elimination of noise pollution effects, and minimal effects of weathering can be achieved (Devine & Halpern, 2001). To this end, the goal of the study is assess event decoration enterprise in Makurdi Metropolis.

1.1. Statement of Problem

The range of possible factors influencing event planning and some degree of decoration is evidently high, especially among competitive decorators (Obadan, Odusola & Akerele, 1996). Current business trends, including globalization and cost pressure which affect many industries worldwide, force most event planning companies to adjust their businesses, focusing on their core markets while trying to stay ahead of the competition by seeking out new business niches, ideas and new revenue. Despite the great potential and positive impacts events decoration companies carried out to the actualization and success of an event, it is faced with challenges like all the other business enterprise (Macfoy, 2021). The current research is therefore poised to assess event decoration

enterprise in Makurdi Metropolis.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this research was the assessment of event decoration enterprise in Makurdi metropolis. Specifically, the study seeks to accomplish the following objectives

- (a) To find out the types of event decoration arrangement in Makurdi metropolis.
- (b) To determine the type of challenges encountered by event decorators in Makurdi metropolis.
- (c) To suggest ways through which these challenges can be minimized to improve event decoration in Makurdi metropolis

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions guided the research:

- (a) What are the types of event decoration arrangement in Makurdi metropolis?
- (b) What are the types of challenges encountered by event decorators in Makurdi metropolis?
- (c) What are the ways through which challenges for event decorators can be improved?

2. Materials and Methods

1.1. Design for the Study

The descriptive survey research design was used for this study. According to Emaikwu (2019) survey research design is a method of collecting data for the purpose of describing a population so large to be observed directly. In this case representative sample was used from which generalization was made on the entire population.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The Department of Home Science and Management at the Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, granted ethical clearance for this study. Respondents' informed consent was received to enable them complete the survey.

2.2. Area of the Study

This study was conducted in Makurdi metropolis. Makurdi metropolis serves as the administrative center of Benue State in Nigeria, situated in the north-central region of the nation. It is positioned along the banks of the River Benue.

2.3. Population and Sample

The population of the study comprise event decorators from the registered 115 event decoration ventures in Makurdi metropolis. The sample for the study constituted 67 respondents. The respondents comprised staff and management of event decoration ventures in Makurdi metropolis from thirty-two (32) major event decorating ventures in Makurdi metropolis. Two sample technique that was used was cluster and simple purposive Cluster sampling was used to select thirty-two event decorating ventures in Makurdi metropolis while purposive sampling was used to sample the respondents in the selected event decorating ventures. For the sake of accuracy of results, purposive sampling was used for this research and this is because, according to Emaikwu (2019) in purposive sampling, specific elements which satisfy some predetermined criteria are selected and these elements include the questionnaire.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from respondents in Makurdi Metropolis. The instrument consists of sections A and B. Section A seeks information on a bio data of respondents while section B consists of eleven (11) items which seeks information on challenges faced by event decorators in Makurdi metropolis.

2.5. Data Analysis Technique

Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The benchmark for the items was 2.50. Any item with a mean value of less than 2.50 was regarded as rejected.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean rating on types of event decoration arrangement in Makurdi metropolis

S/N	Types of event decoration	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Fabric arranged decoration (drapes)	3.74	.53	Accepted
2	Flower arranged decoration	3.65	.62	Accepted
3	Balloon arranged decoration	3.47	.64	Accepted
4	Ornamental arranged decoration	1.51	.77	Accepted
5	Candle arranged decoration	2.52	.63	Accepted
6	Colourful lamps decoration	2.63	.68	Accepted

From the study, research question 1 was to find out the types of arrangement in event decoration. The fabric arranged decoration was the highest with mean rating of 3.74. The highest rating for the choice of fabric for decoration was in line with Ergüden (2012) who stated that soft furnishing for decoration is the best. Fabrics can be reused several times for decoration purposes. The least was the ornamental arranged decoration with a mean score of 1.51, this was as a result of time consuming for arranging ornaments during and after the event. This statement was in agreement with Githiri (2016) and Çetinsöz (2019) who stated that physical environment has influence on consumer satisfaction.

Table 2: Mean rating on types of Challenges encountered by event decorators in Makurdi Metropolis

S/N	Types of challenges	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Budgetary challenges	3.81	.47	Accepted
2	Poor management	3.72	.57	Accepted
3	Financial problem	3.25	.68	Accepted
4	Materials challenge	2.96	.68	Accepted
5	Lack of Manpower	2.52	.80	Accepted
6	Technical challenge	1.87	.77	Rejected

Research question two was to examine the types of challenges encountered by event decorators. Result showed that the budgetary challenges, and the material challenges, was rated high. Budgetary challenges had a mean rating of 3.81 which is the highest mean. This result is in conformity with the findings of Arnold et al.(2003) who found that budget approval improve the overall success of the event decoration and it should be utilized to avoid pitfalls in future projects. The statement is also in conformity with the study of Pivac et al. (2011) on consumer satisfaction of event management

service in tourism industry.

Table 3: Possible ways through which these challenges can be minimized to improve event decorators in Makurdi metropolis

S/N	Possible ways to minimize challenges	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Careful budget planning	3.67	.72	Accepted
2	Use of quality materials for decoration	3.66	.44	Accepted
3	Training of individuals and innovation	3.47	.60	Accepted
4	Providing adequate welfare for workers	3.36	.97	Accepted
5	Good managerial skills and risk bearing	3.22	.83	Accepted

Research question three seeks to determine ways in which these challenges in event decoration can be improved. From the results in table three, shows that careful budget planning had the highest mean rating of 3.67, followed by the use of quality materials while decorating with a mean of 3.66. This finding has a similar resemblance with the finding of Bitner (1990) who found that despite the great potentials and positive impact event management ventures have, it is faced with challenges and these challenges can be reduced if proper steps are taken such as ensuring that the budgetary unit is properly planned and executed.

4. Conclusion

Balloon, flower and the fabric event decorations were the most practiced in Makurdi metropolis. Majority of event decorators were faced with challenges of material availability, technical challenges and challenges of skillful manpower. Careful budget planning and managerial risk bearing was the key to successful business enterprise in the state. Fabric decoration was rated high in the study, so it is recommended that large quantities of assorted fabric colours and designs should be manufactured locally to meet high demand for event decoration. In order to minimize the challenges faced by event decorators, they should be very careful while planning their budgets. Event decorators should always ensure they use the best materials for decoration. Event decorator should constantly update their skill by training and finding out new styles, designs and apply them during decoration at events.

Acknowledgements

None

Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflict of interest to declare.

Author Contributions

All the research procedures including conceptualization, methodology, study design, data collection, analysis, writing and revision were done by the author. Final version of this article was approved by the author.

Data Availability Statement

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article

Funding Information

No funding to disclose

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Publisher: Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria

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